

Short Communication**Gastrointestinal Parasites of Locally Reared Chickens Slaughtered in Birnin Kebbi Market, Kebbi State, Nigeria**

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Abstract

In an attempt to ensure availability and access to good food, this paper delves into the gastrointestinal parasites that infect locally reared chickens slaughtered in Birnin Kebbi central market. A total of one hundred intestinal tracts of chickens was examined using the formal ether concentration technique. The predominant specie of the parasites recovered were Eimeria praecox, 47(47 %), Strongyloides avium 24(24%), Ascaridia galli 19(19%) and Raillientina tetragon 7(7%). Female chickens were significantly more infected 19(82.61%) than male chickens 50(64.94%). The observed difference between weight and parasitic infection was not statistically significant ($p>0.05$). However, the overall prevalence of the infection recorded in this study was 69(69.00%) while 22(22.00%) of the infected chickens had mixed infection. This result indicates the need for proper hygienic rearing system for the chickens in order to curtail the threat of parasitic infections and ensure availability of safe eggs and meat production for the teeming population.

Key words: Local chickens, Helminthes, Parasite Safety.

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Introduction

Locally or extensive free range management type of poultry production represent significant portion of affordable source of meat and egg for most Nigerians. Although this traditional poultry production system is characterized by low input, low output and periodic distribution of large portion of the flock due to outbreak of disease (Eshetu *et al.*, 2001). Yet the locally reared chicken appeared to be more tolerable to high environmental

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temperature and dry condition of northern areas compared to exotic breed chicken (Yoriyo *et al.* 2008).

FAO reported that daily protein requirement is 65g/caput per day and about 35g of this protein supposed to be of animal protein accounting for only 8g/cap per day, representing a shortfall of about 77% in animal protein recommended (FAO, 2010). Free ranging chickens, from rural areas supply almost all of the chicken's meat and egg requirement and of about 12 to 13% of urban requirement in order to meet the desire and sufficient demand for food production.

Major constraints that hinder the development of this management system, and the production of food from this food requirement is intestinal parasitism. Reports from within Nigeria indicated that gastrointestinal helminth parasites constitute the most important group of parasite both in number of species and amount of damage done to locally reared chickens (Fatihu *et al.*, 1991; Biu and Haddabi, 2005; Yoriyo *et al.*, 2008;). However, on a worldwide scale, coccidiosis in chickens was reported as the most severe and frequently recorded poultry disease (Thebo *et al.*, 1998). Locally reared chickens satisfy their nutrient requirements by roaming from place to place and they usually seek their food in the superficial layers of the soil which is contaminated with living organism of all kinds, including various insects or earthworms which serve as paratenic or intermediate host of helminths (Hussen *et al.*, 2004). For coccidiosis, the infective oocysts are excreted in faeces which are later consumed along with food or drinks. This exposed the chickens to many challenges such as parasitic infections.

Clinical signs of parasitism as recorded by Aini, (2000) are unfitness, poor growth and feed conversion, decrease egg production, and even death in severe infection. Furthermore, parasites can make the flock less resistant to disease and exacerbate existing disease condition. Young birds are often more severely infected. Although mild infection is often not noticed, a number of worms can interfere with feed absorption causing poor growth and development. In severe infection there could be intestinal blockage by worms, causing death.

Presently, there is scantiness of records on the gastrointestinal parasites of local chickens in the study area. It is also necessary to assess the parasite status of locally reared chickens from time to time so as to check the distribution of these parasites. This study therefore, seeks to reveal the prevalence of gastrointestinal parasites of locally reared chickens slaughtered in Birnin Kebbi market, Kebbi State.

Materials and Method

Study area

Birnin Kebbi is the Capital of Kebbi State in North-Western Nigeria. The State was created from parts of Sokoto State in 1991. Kebbi State is bordered by Sokoto State, Niger State, Dosso region in the republic of Niger and the nation of Benin. It has a total area of 36,800 km². The chickens used in this study were gotten from the town's main market. The approach was that the health status of chickens slaughtered in this market could reasonably reflect the actual situation in both urban and rural areas where these animals originated.

Sample collection

A total number of one hundred (100) locally reared chickens slaughtered in Birnin Kebbi market were studied for intestinal parasite between 24th and 28th of July, 2012. A total number of 25 guts were collected on a daily basis. The consent of the buyer and seller were sought for prior to slaughtering. The sex of the chickens and the weight of the chickens (in kg) were recorded. The guts were obtained after the dissection and placed in a sterile container. The samples were then transported to the microbiology laboratory of Waziri Umaru Federal Polytechnic in Birnin Kebbi for immediate parasitological analysis.

Laboratory analysis

Identification of adult worm

The gastrointestinal tracts were separated into small intestine (ileum and duodenum) and caeca. Each alimentary tract was spread on a dissecting board and the content was scrapped into Petri dishes containing 0.9% physiological saline. The lumen of each section was opened longitudinally to expose its content as described by Fatihu *et al.* (1991). The content was then observed under a microscope for helminths. Counting of the collected worms was done with the aid of a pair of forceps and the morphological appearance of the parasites aided the separation into tape worms and round worms. Each group was then separated into different Petri dishes. The microscope was used for counting. Worms from each section were isolated, counted and preserved in labelled vials containing 10% formalin prior to identification.

Concentration technique

The formal ether concentration technique as described by Cheesebrough (2008), was also used. 10ml of 10% formalin was poured into a test tube, an estimated 2g of intestinal content were added and stirred using an applicator stick until a lightly cloudy suspension was made. A gauze funnel was fitted and placed on top of a conical test tube. The

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suspension was poured through the filter into a centrifuge tube until 7ml mark was reached. The filter was removed and discarded with the suspension residue. A 4ml of ethyl acetate was added and the test tube was shaken back and front for many times. The stopper was carefully removed and centrifuged for one minute. An applicator stick was used to loosen the fatty plug (i.e. the debris layer), and the supernatant were poured away by quickly inverting the tube. It was mixed well and a drop was transferred to a slide and was examined under a cover slip.

The preparation was examined using 10x and 40x objective of light microscope for the presence of ova, cysts and larvae of parasite.

Identification of parasites

Parasites were examined and identified microscopically and by using references of Soulsby (1982), Khalil *et al.*, (1994) and Donald *et al.*, (1998).

Data Analysis

The term prevalence was calculated as described by Margolis *et al.*, (1982) and expressed as a percentage (%). Chi-square test was employed to determine the association between prevalence and sex and weight.

Results

Prevalence of Parasites Detected Among Infected Chickens

The predominant species of parasites found was *Eimeria praecox* with 47(47%) infected chickens, *Strongyloides avium* with 24(24%) infected chickens, *Ascaridia galli* 19(19%) infected chickens, and finally *Raillietina tetragona* 7(7%) (Table: 1). At 5% level of significance, there is a significant difference between parasitic species and prevalence of infection among chicken examined in Birnin Kebbi Market.

Table 1: Prevalence of Parasites Detected Among Infected Chickens

Specie of Parasites	Number examined	Number infected	Percentage infected (%)
<i>Eimeria praecox</i>	100	47	47.00
<i>Strongyloides avium</i>	100	24	24.00
<i>Ascaridia galli</i>	100	19	19.00
<i>Raillietina tetragona</i>	100	7	7.00

Sex Prevalence of the Infection Among Chickens

A total number of 50 (64.94%) out of 77 male chicken examined were positive while 19 (82.61%) out of 23 female chicken were positive. (Table 2).

At 5% level of significant there is a significance difference among the infected male and the female chicken.

Table 2: Sex Prevalence of the Infection Among the Chickens

Sex of chickens	Number examined	Number of infected	Percentage (%)
Male	77	50	64.94
Female	23	19	82.61
Total	100	69	69.00

Weight prevalence of the infection among chickens

Table 3 shows that 24 (66.67%) out of 36 chickens weighed between 2-2.99kg were infected 36 (73.47%) out of 49 chickens weighed between 3-3.99kg were infected while 9 (60%) out of 15 chickens were infected. At 5% level of significance there is no relationship between the prevalence of gastrointestinal parasites and weight.

Table 3: Weight Prevalence of the Infection Among Chickens

Weight of chicken	Number examined	Number infected	Percentage (%)
2-2.99kg	36	24	66.67
3-3.99kg	49	36	73.47
4-4.99kg	15	9	60.00
Total	100	69	69.00

Total Prevalence of Gastrointestinal Parasites Among Chickens Examined

Table 4 Shows that among sixty-nine (69) chickens infected, 22 (22.00%) had mixed infection, while 31(31%) of the total chickens examined were not infected with any parasites.

Table 4: Total Prevalence of Gastrointestinal Parasites Among Chickens Examined

Number examined	Mixed infection	Single infection	Number Infected	Not infected
100	22	47	69	31
Percentage %	22.00	47.00	69.00	31.00

Discussion

This study revealed that 69.00% of the chickens examined were infected with one or more helminth parasite. This prevalence is similar to the findings of Rufai and Jato (2017) from Iwo, Osun State, Nigeria (62%). It is however low when compared with the findings of Alam *et al.*, (2014) Maina *et al.*, (2017) and Mebrahtu Berhe *et al.*, (2019) from Bangladesh, Kenya and Ethiopia respectively. The high prevalence (69%) rate of gastrointestinal parasites encountered in Birnin Kebbi could be due to the fact that chickens kept under free range satisfy their nutrient requirements by roaming from place to place and they usually seek their food in the superficial layers of the soil which is contaminated with living organism of all kind, including various insects or earth worm which serve as paratenic or intermediate host of helminths (Hussen *et al.*, 2012), and this increases the chances of becoming infected.

Eimeria praecox which is the only protozoan parasite encountered was the predominant parasite encountered with 47(47%) infected chickens. A similar observation has been made by Wokem and Obiyor (2018) who recorded 41.5% *Eimeria species* among commercial layers in Rivers State, Nigeria. This parasite was noted to cause pathological lesions along the intestinal mucosa of the chickens examined. This lends a credence to previous report made by Thebo *et al.*, (2012) that *Eimeria* are known to infect the caeca with deep development in the mucosa and subsequent wide spread done with distinct gross lesion and loss of blood in faeces. However, the high prevalence of *E. praecox* encountered in this study and others, such as that of Fabiyi (1972) could be attributed to the fact that locally reared chickens are suitable host for the parasite (Tailor and Francis, 2009). Although this species has been noted to be less pathogenic than other causative agent of coccidiosis (Thebo *et al.*, 2012) coccidiosis is rated as a non-eradicable disease (De Gussem, 2005). This is a cause for a serious alarm on food security of the nation as coccidiosis has also been identified in all parts of the world as deadly disease of flock with resultant economic losses (Bachaya *et al.* 2012).

Strongyloides avium 24 (24%) and *Ascaridia galli* 19 (19%), group of nematode parasites and *Raillietina tetragona* 7(7%) a cestode were the group of helminth parasites recovered in this study. This observation was synonymous with the findings of Hussien *et al.*, (2012) that, helminth parasites infect scavenging chickens worldwide with mixed infection being very common. This is, however, in contrast with the findings of Ayeh-Kumi *et al.* (2016) somewhere in Ghana in which mixed being infection was less common. Similar reports were documented from other parts of Nigeria (Fabiya, 1972; Fatihu *et al.*, 1991; Bui and Haddabi, 2005; Yoriyo *et al.*, 2008 and Idika *et al.*, 2015). The helminths parasites are known to compete for nutrient with the host chickens and thereby cause inflammation and lesions in the intestinal tract and this interferes with digestion and assimilation of nutrients by the host (Irungu *et al.*, 2004).

Female chickens were more significantly infected ($p < 0.05$) than the males in this study. The higher prevalence in female chickens could be attributed to their voracious habit of feeding especially during egg production than the males which remain largely selective (Matur *et al.*, 2010).

The weight and infection revealed that 36 (73.47%) out of 49 infected chickens between weight of 3-3.99kg were infected and 24 (66.77%) out of 36 infected chickens between weight of 2-2.99kg were infected, with least prevalence among chickens that weighed 4-4.99kg. However, the differences in this study were not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). In conclusion, locally reared chicken in Birnin Kebbi and its environs are exposed to gastrointestinal parasites like *Eimeria species* and some helminthes. It is hereby recommended that more attention should be focused on the improvement of poultry management and care of local breed chickens which are usually free ranging by ensuring proper hygienic rearing system, observing their health condition and attending to their veterinary needs, and supplementing their feeds with energy sources. This could curtail the threat of parasitic infections and ensure availability of safe eggs and meat production to meet the protein requirement of the teeming population.

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